

Kinetics of Oxidation of Thiosemicarbazide in the Metal Complex by Iodamine-T, Iodine Monochloride and Iodine in Aqueous Perchloric Acid Medium

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Kinetics of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide (TSC) in its zinc metal complex, $Zn(TSC)_2SO_4$, by iodamine-T, iodine monochloride and iodine have been studied in aqueous perchloric acid medium. Oxidation of the ligand followed the common rate law,

$$-d[\text{oxidant}]/dt = k[\text{oxidant}][\text{complex}]/(1 + K[\text{complex}] + K[H^+])$$

with all the oxidants. Dependence of rate on [TSC] decreased on metal complexation of the ligand in iodamine-T oxidation, while it increased in ICl and I_2 oxidations. Increase in ionic strength of the medium slightly decreased the rate in all the cases. Decrease in dielectric constant of the medium increased the rate with iodamine-T and had no effect with the other two oxidants. Oxidation process has been shown to follow Michaelis-Menten type mechanism in accordance with the observed rate law.

THE reactions of thiosemicarbazides are of interest due to their biological importance and wide chemical applications^{1,2}. As a part of our mechanistic investigations with biologically active substrates in general and thiosemicarbazide reactions in particular³⁻⁵, we report herein the kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide (TSC) in its zinc metal complex by iodamine-T, iodine monochloride and iodine in aqueous perchloric acid medium.

Although a number of oxidants have been employed as analytical reagents for its determinations in pure state and in its metal complexes⁶, there are very few reports on the mechanistic aspects of thiosemicarbazide reactions^{3,4}.

Experimental

Analytical grade (Merck) samples of iodine and iodine monochloride were used. Iodamine-T (*N*-iodo-*N*-potassiotoluene-*p*-sulphonamide) (IAT, RNIK) was prepared by literature method⁷. The purity of iodamine-T was checked by its spectra and iodometric estimation of the amount of active iodine present in it. Stock solutions (~ 0.1 mol dm^{-3}) of iodine (in aqueous KI), iodine monochloride (aqueous) and iodamine-T (in 0.1 mol dm^{-3} KOH) were prepared, standardised and stored in dark-coloured bottles.

Thiosemicarbazide (E. Merck) was recrystallised from water. The complex, $Zn(TSC)_2SO_4$ was prepared by mixing the concentrated aqueous solutions of TSC and zinc sulphate in 2 : 1 molar ratio. The complex was recrystallised from water

and characterised by its spectra, elemental analysis and analytical estimations⁸. A stock solution of the complex (0.02 mol dm^{-3}) in 0.03 mol dm^{-3} $HClO_4$ was prepared.

The ionic strength of the reaction medium was maintained at 0.3 mol dm^{-3} with sodium perchlorate (E. Merck). All other reagents used were of accepted grades of purity.

Kinetic measurements: The kinetic runs were made in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes under pseudo-first order reaction conditions. The reactions were initiated by rapid additions of measured amounts of oxidant solution (thermostated at the desired temperatures) to reaction mixtures containing requisite quantities of TSC or complex, $HClO_4$ and sodium perchlorate solutions and water pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric method for two half-lives. The pseudo-first order rate constants (k_{obs}) were computed by the graphical methods and the values were reproducible within $\pm 3\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis: The stoichiometries of complex-IAT, complex-ICl and complex- I_2 reactions were determined by allowing the reactions to go to completion at different [complex]/[oxidant] ratios and [$HClO_4$] (0.01–0.20 mol dm^{-3}). The products, sulphate and cyanate in the reaction with IAT and ICl were detected by standard tests^{8,9}. Sulphate was quantitatively determined by the gravimetric method¹⁰. Toluene-*p*-sulphonamide (TSA), the reduced product of IAT was detected by paper chromatography. The

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observed stoichiometries per mole of ligand TSC may be represented by equations (1-3).

where, Ar=CH₃C₆H₄. Under the experimental conditions employed in iodine oxidations, HNCS produced would be around 0.0005 mol dm⁻³. It has been observed that the oxidation of HNCS by I₂ is very sluggish at these concentrations.

Results and Discussion

Kinetics of oxidation of thiosemicarbazide in its metal complex Zn(TSC)₂SO₄ by iodamine-T, iodine monochloride and aqueous iodine were studied at several initial [oxidant] and [complex] over a wide range of [HClO₄] (0.01-0.20 mol dm⁻³). At fixed [HClO₄], with several fold excess of the complex (~20 times), plots of log [oxidant]₀/[oxidant] vs time were linear at least for two half-lives for all the oxidants (Fig. 1) and the pseudo-first order rate constants were unaffected by the changes in [oxidant]₀ (Table 1), showing first order kinetics in [oxidant] in all cases. The rates increased with the increase in [complex] at constant [oxidant] and [H⁺] and decreased with increase in [HClO₄] at constant [oxidant]₀ and [complex]₀. The orders

Fig. 1. (A) Plots of log [KI] vs time and (B) plot of log [I₂] vs time; [complex]₀=4.0 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³, [HClO₄]=1.06 × 10 mol dm⁻³; I=0.80 mol dm⁻³; [oxidant]₀(× 10⁴ mol dm⁻³)=(a) 1.0, (b) 2.0, (c) 4.0, (d) 8.0.

TABLE 1—*k*_{obs} VALUES FOR OXIDATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE IN ITS ZINC METAL COMPLEX BY IODAMINE-T (IAT), ICl AND I₂ IN AQUEOUS HClO₄ MEDIUM

Temp.=303 K, I=0.8 mol dm⁻³

[oxidant] ₀ × 10 ⁴ mol dm ⁻³	[complex] ₀ × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	[HClO ₄] × 10 mol dm ⁻³	<i>k</i> _{obs} (× 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹)		
			IAT	IOI	I ₂ *
(i) Effect of varying [oxidant]₀					
1.0	4.0	1.06	2.8	2.8	3.4
2.0	4.0	1.06	2.8	2.8	3.4
4.0	4.0	1.06	2.8	2.8	3.4
8.0	4.0	1.06	2.8	2.8	3.4
(ii) Effect of varying [complex]₀					
2.0	1.0	1.06	1.9	1.8	2.0
2.0	2.0	1.06	2.4	1.8	2.6
2.0	4.0	1.06	2.8	2.8	3.4
2.0	8.0	1.06	3.5	3.0	4.3
2.0	10.0	1.06	3.7	3.3	4.6
(iii) Effect of varying [HClO₄]					
2.0	4.0	0.16	—	12.6	15.8
2.0	4.0	0.26	—	7.8	9.8
2.0	4.0	0.31	6.8	—	—
2.0	4.0	0.46	—	4.8	6.0
2.0	4.0	0.56	4.3	—	—
2.0	4.0	1.06	2.8	2.8	3.4
2.3	4.0	1.56	2.9	—	—
2.0	4.0	2.06	2.0	1.5	2.2

[KI]=0.02 mol dm⁻³.

in [complex] and $[H^+]$ were evaluated from the log-log plots of rate constants (k_{obs}) vs [complex] or $[H^+]$ (Tables 1-3).

TABLE 2—EFFECTS OF VARIATIONS IN IONIC STRENGTH AND DIELECTRIC CONSTANT OF REACTION MEDIUM AND ADDITION OF REACTION PRODUCTS ON RATES OF OXIDATIONS OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE IN $Zn(TSC)_2SO_4$ BY IODAMINE-T (IAT), IOI AND I_2 IN $HClO_4$ MEDIUM*

Temp. = 303 K			
I mol dm ⁻³	k_{obs} ($\times 10^4$ s ⁻¹)		
	IAT	IOI	I_2
0.11	3.2	2.8	4.2
0.20	3.0	2.5	3.9
0.30	2.8	2.3	3.4
0.50	2.5	2.2	3.1
D			
76.6	2.8	2.8	3.4
72.1	4.6	2.3	3.4
67.6	5.6	2.3	3.4
58.6	6.9	2.5	3.4
[TSA] ($\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³)			
0.0	2.8	—	—
0.1	2.8	—	—
0.5	2.9	—	—
1.0	2.9	—	—
[KI] (or [KCl]) ($\times 10$ mol dm ⁻³)			
0.0	2.8	2.8	3.4
1.0	3.1	2.4	3.6
5.0	4.8	2.8	3.9
10.0	6.9	3.1	4.1
20.0	9.5	—	—

*[oxidant]₀ = 2.0×10^4 mol dm⁻³, [complex]₀ = 4.0×10^3 mol dm⁻³, $[HClO_4]$ = 1.06×10 mol dm⁻³, $I = 0.8$ mol dm⁻³ (except during its variation). *With IOI.

TABLE 3—KINETIC AND ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR OXIDATION OF THIOSEMICARBAZIDE IN $Zn(TSC)_2SO_4$ BY IODAMINE-T (IAT), IOI AND I_2 * MONOCHLORIDE AND IODINE

Orders observed in	IAT	IOI	I_2
[Oxidant] ₀	1(1)	1(1)	1(1)
[Complex] ₀ or [TSC] ₀	0.25(0.2-0.4)	0.38(0.25)	0.38(0.14)
$[H^+]$	-0.62(-1.0)	-0.75(-0.81)	-0.65(-0.53)
Parameters			
log A	8.8	8.4(11.3)	9.0(10.1)
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	68.9	69.7(86.2)	72.3(80.8)
$\Delta H^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	66.4	67.2(83.6)	69.8(78.9)
$\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-20.6	-20.1(-6.5)	-17.4(-12.3)
$\Delta G^\ddagger$ (kJ mol ⁻¹)	72.6	73.3(85.8)	75.1(81.7)

*Values in parenthesis are parameters for oxidation of TSC in free state.

The increase in ionic strength of the medium slightly decreased the rate with all the oxidants (Table 2), while the decrease in dielectric constant of the medium by changing the solvent composition with methanol slightly increased the rate with iodamine-T and had no effect with iodine monochloride and iodine (Table 2). Addition of the reaction products, I⁻, Cl⁻ (with IOI) and TSA (with iodamine-T) had little or no effect on the

rate with all the oxidants, but the addition of I⁻ increased the rate with IAT.

The rates of reactions were measured at different temperatures and the activation parameters calculated (Table 3).

Iodamine-T (ArSO₂NiK) is analogous to chloramine-T¹¹⁻¹³ and bromamine-B¹⁴ in aqueous solutions. ArSO₂NH₂I⁺ and H₂OI⁺ are the probable reactive species in its aqueous acid solutions (around 0.10 mol dm⁻³).

Mechanism of oxidations: Kinetics of first order dependences in [oxidant], fractional order in [TSC] or $[Zn(TSC)_2SO_4]$ and inverse fractional order in $[H^+]$ observed with all the oxidants may be explained by Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

Based on Scheme 1, rate law (4) has been deduced,

$$\text{Rate} = -\frac{d[\text{oxidant}]}{dt} = k_3 [\text{complex}]$$

$$= \frac{k_3 K_2 [\text{oxidant}]_0 [S]}{1 + K_1 [H^+] + K_2 [S]} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{or, } k_{obs} = \frac{k_3 K_2 [S]'}{1 + K_1 [H^+] + K_2 [S]} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{or, } \frac{1}{k_{obs}} = \frac{1 + K_1 [H^+]}{k_3 K_2 [S]} + \frac{1}{k_3} \quad (6)$$

$$= \frac{K_1 [H^+]}{k_3 K_2 [S]} + \frac{1 + K_2 [S]}{k_3 K_2 [S]} \quad (7)$$

The plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[S]$ and $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[H^+]$ were linear in accordance with rate law (7) (Fig. 2). The reciprocal of the intercept of the former plot gave k_3 .

A detailed mechanism of oxidation of TSC in zinc metal complex is shown in Scheme 2. Comparison of kinetic data for the oxidation of TSC in the free state and in its metal complex reveals that the zinc complexation of the substrate increases the dependence of the rate on TSC with IOI and I_2 .

With iodamine-T and iodine monochloride, substrate to oxidant stoichiometry observed was around 1 : 6, which corresponds to the formation of N₂, SO₂²⁻ and CNO⁻ as products. An alternate scheme showing the formation of N₂, SO₂²⁻, CO₂ and ammonia may also be proposed, but CO₂ and NH₃ are formed as minor products. Their relative formations also varied with the oxidants. With iodine 1 : 2 stoichiometry observed corresponds

Fig. 2. (i) Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $1/[complex]$: (●) IAT, (○) IOI and (◇) I_2 ; $[oxidant]_0 = 2.0 \times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[HClO_4] = 1.06 \times 10 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; Temp. = 303 K. (ii) Plots of $1/k_{obs}$ vs $[H^+]$: (▲) IAT, (◆) IOI, and (◇) I_2 ; $10^4 [oxidant]_0 = 2.0 \times 10^4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $[complex]_0 = 4.0 \times 10^8 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, $I = 0.80 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, Temp. = 303 K.

to the formation of thiocyanate as the product. Under the experimental conditions the product formed would be around $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. As already pointed out, oxidation of thiocyanate by iodine is sluggish at these concentrations.

The rate constant (k_D) for an ion-molecule reaction in a medium of dielectric constant D is given by equation (8)¹⁵,

$$\ln k_D = \ln k_\infty + \frac{Z_o \mu_o}{KT r^2 D} \quad (8)$$

where, k_∞ is the rate constant in a medium of infinite dielectric constant, Z_o the charge on the ion, μ the permanent moment on the dipolar molecule, r the radius of the ion and T the absolute temperature. Equation (8) predicts a linearity between $\log k_D$ and $1/D$ with a positive slope if Z is positive, and negative slope if Z is negative. Slight increase of rate with the decrease in dielectric constant of the reaction medium observed with iodamine-T is in accordance with this concept as the reaction path may involve interaction between protonated TSC and HOI. Further, the plots of $\log_{obs}$ vs $1/D$ was linear with a positive slope (figure not shown).

The observed little decrease of rate with the increase in ionic strength of the medium is in accordance with Quinlan-Amis equation¹⁶ for ion-dipolar molecule reaction.

References

1. M. J. M. CAMPBELL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, 15, 279.
2. M. A. ALI and S. E. LIVINGSTONE, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1974, 13, 101.
3. B. T. GOWDA and J. I. BHAT, *React. Kinet. Catal. Lett.*, 1986, 31, 461; *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 1129, 1149; 1987, 26, 215; 1988, 27; *Tetrahedron*, 1987, 43, 2119; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1986, 63, 665; 1987, 64, 150; 1988, 65, 159.
4. B. T. GOWDA and R. V. RAO, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, 24, 1021; 1986, 25, 578, 908; 1988, 27, 84, 89; *Oxidn. Commun.*, 1987, 10, 31; 1988, 11, 45; *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1987, 355; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 64, 403, 467, 474.
5. B. T. GOWDA and B. S. SHERRIGARA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1986, 25, 960; 1987, 26, 980; 1988, 27; *Oxidn. Commun.*, 1986, 9, 165; *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1987, 64, 158; 1988, 65.
6. B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *Microchem. J.*, 1983, 28, 374.
7. C. P. K. PILLAI and P. INDRASENAN, *Talanta*, 1980, 27, 751.
8. F. FREGLI, "Spot Tests in Inorganic Analysis", 5th. ed., Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1958.
9. E. A. WERNER, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 128, 2577.
10. A. I. VOGEL, "Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", Longmans, London, 1964.
11. E. BISHOP and V. J. JENNINGS, *Talanta*, 1958, 1, 197.
12. M. M. CAMPBELL and G. JOHNSON, *Chem. Rev.*, 1978, 78, 65.
13. B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin. Trans. 2*, 1989, 323.
14. F. E. HARDY and J. P. JOHNSTON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin. Trans. 2*, 1973, 742.
15. E. S. AMIS, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic, New York, 1966.
16. J. E. QUINLAN and E. S. AMIS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 4187.